

Freely Falling Body due to Gravity: Equality of Potential and Kinetic Energy

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Abstract: This paper proves that the kinetic energy of a freely falling object due to gravity is equal to the potential energy of the object at a specific point in a straight-line motion.

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The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation

In classical mechanics, the potential energy and the potential energy of a freely falling body due to gravity are not always equal, but they are numerically equal at an exact location in its motion. However, the sum of potential energy and kinetic energy of the freely falling object remains constant throughout the motion due to the principle of conservation of energy.

Now, let us prove that the kinetic energy of a freely falling object with non-zero mass (m), velocity (v), and gravitational acceleration (g) at a fixed point, where h is the height from the fixed point to the ground, is equal to the potential energy of the object.

The equations of motion including potential and kinetic energy are given below:

Kinetic energy (K) = $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and potential energy (P) = mgh .

Let us prove that $P = K$.

$$P = mgh. \quad (1)$$

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = 0 + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}gt^2. \quad (2)$$

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2gh \Rightarrow v^2 = 0 + 2gh \Rightarrow v^2 = 2g\left(\frac{1}{2}gt^2\right) \Rightarrow v^2 = g^2t^2. \quad (3)$$

By substituting the equation (2) in the equation (1), we get

$$P = mg \times h \Rightarrow P = mg \times \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2. \quad (4)$$

By substituting the equation (3) in the equation (4), we conclude that

$$P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K. \quad (5)$$

Hence, it is proved that the potential energy is equal to the kinetic energy of the object.

In addition, the following references [1-20] give more information regarding the energy of an object in motion.

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